

A Kinetic Study on the Complexation Reactions of Nickel-, Cobalt- and Copper(II) with L-2-Aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide

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Because of the immense biological importance of asparagine and wide range of biological processes metals are involved in, we have undertaken the kinetic study of the complexation of asparagine with metal ions, like Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II}. Review of the literature¹⁻³ reveals that although a number of kinetic studies of amino acids with metal ions have been carried out, very little work has been done on the complexation of L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide. Previous studies on the complexation of L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide were done only with Ni^{II} at 25° but nothing has been said about the activation parameters.

In the present study we have calculated K_{os} (outer sphere complex formation constant), k_o (rate constant of water loss) and activation parameters corresponding to the interaction of protonated and deprotonated forms of the ligand.

Results and Discussion

Interaction of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide : Ni^{II} and Co^{II} were taken in large excess over the ligand to ensure pseudo-first order conditions and complete formation of mono-complex only. The reactions were found to be of first order with respect to metal ions and the ligand as the plots of k'_{obs} vs concentrations of metal ions and the ligand were found to be linear. L-2-Aminobutanedioic acid-4-amide has one amino group, one carboxylic group and one amido group. Stability constants³ show that amido group does not participate in the complexation reactions with metal ions.

Kinetics of the interaction of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with L-2-aminobutanedioic acid-4-amide was investigated in the pH range 6.23–7.12 at $I = 0.1 M$ KNO₃ and at 25–40° (± 0.05°). Dissociation of L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide can be represented as

The diprotonated (HN⁺-OH), monoprotonated (HN⁺-O⁻) and deprotonated (N-O⁻) forms can react with M(II) in a stepwise manner as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The rate equation for the interaction of M(II) with L-2-aminobutanedioic acid-4-amide can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= -\frac{d}{dt} [M(II)] \\ &= -\frac{d}{dt} [\text{L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide}] \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$= k_{\text{obs}} [M(II)] [\text{L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide}] \quad (2)$$

$$= k'_{\text{obs}} [\text{L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide}] \quad (3)$$

$$= k'_{\text{obs}} \{ [\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}] + [\text{H}^+ \text{N}-\text{O}^-] + [\text{N}-\text{O}^-] \} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where, } k'_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{obs}} [M(II)] \quad (5)$$

Scheme 1 is different from the scheme given by Voss and Jordan² who did not take into account the dissociation of diprotonated form of the ligand. From Scheme 1 the rate of reaction can be written as

$$\text{Rate} = k_{35} [\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] \quad (6)$$

Using the steady state approximation for unstable intermediates $\text{HN}^+-\text{O}-\text{M}^+$ and $\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{M}^+$ we get

$$\begin{aligned} d/dt [\text{HN}^+-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] &= k_{12} [\text{HN}^+-\text{O}^-] [M(II)] - k_{21} [\text{HN}^+-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] \\ &\quad - k_{23} [\text{HN}^+-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] + k_{32} [\text{H}^+] [\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} d/dt [\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] &= k_{43} [\text{N}-\text{O}^-] [M(II)] - k_{34} [\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] \\ &\quad - k_{32} [\text{H}^+] [\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] + k_{23} [\text{HN}^+-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] - k_{35} \\ &\quad [\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

From Scheme 1,

$$[\text{HN}^+-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] = k_{32}/k_{23} [\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{M}^+] [\text{H}^+] \quad (9)$$

Adding equation (7) and (8), using equation (9) and on rearrangement, we get the value of $[\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{M}^+]$. Substituting the value of $[\text{N}-\text{O}-\text{M}^+]$ in equation (6), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \\ &= \frac{k_{12} k_{23} k_{35} [\text{HN}^+-\text{O}^-] + k_{23} k_{43} k_{35} [\text{N}-\text{O}^-] [M(II)]}{k_{21} k_{32} [\text{H}^+] + k_{23} (k_{34} + k_{35})} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Using from Scheme 1, the values of $[\text{HN}^+-\text{O}^-]$ and $[\text{N}-\text{O}^-]$ in terms of $[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}]$ and after rearrangement, equation (10) reduces to equation (11),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{k_{12} k_{23} k_{35} K_1 [\text{H}^+] + k_{23} k_{35} k_{43} K_1 K_2}{k_{21} k_{32} [\text{H}^+] + k_{23} (k_{34} + k_{35})} \\ &= \frac{[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}] [M(II)]}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Substituting the values of $[\text{HN}^+-\text{O}^-]$ and $[\text{N}-\text{O}^-]$ in terms of $[\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}]$ in equation (4) and on rearrangement we get

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= k_{\text{obs}} \frac{M(II) [\text{HN}^+-\text{OH}]}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \\ &= \frac{\{ [\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 \}}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

At high pH, $k_{12} k_{32} [\text{H}^+] \ll k_{23} (k_{34} + k_{35})$ and in case of normal substitution⁵ $k_{35} > k_{34}$, applying these approximations and comparing equations (11) and (12) we get

$$k_{\text{obs}} \frac{\{ [\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 \}}{K_1 [\text{H}^+]} = k_{12} + \frac{K_2 k_{43}}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (13)$$

The values of k_{12} and k_{43} (Table 1) have been obtained from the intercepts and slopes of the linear plots of left-hand-side value of equation (13) vs $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ at different temperatures. The plots of Ni^{II} -L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide interaction are shown as representative case in Fig. 1. The values of K_1 and K_2 were taken from the literature and corrected for different temperatures using the thermodynamic relation,

$$pK_a^{T_2} = \frac{\Delta H_a(T_2 - T_1)}{4.576 T_1 T_2} + pK_a^{T_1} \quad (14)$$

Activation parameter values were calculated from the slopes and intercepts of the plots of $\log k$ and $\log k/T$ vs $1/T$. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger corresponding to k_{12} and k_{43} steps for Ni -L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide were found to be 58.12, 16.32 kJ mol^{-1} and -12.01, -106.69 $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$ respectively, and for Co -L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide were found to be 22.18, 11.51 kJ mol^{-1} and -113.05, -114.10 $\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$ respectively.

On the basis of the generally accepted mechanism⁶ for the metal complexation reactions, the rate can be written as

$$\text{Rate} = K_{\text{os}} k_{\text{o}} [M(II)] [L] \quad (15)$$

where K_{os} is the outer-sphere complex formation constant, and k_o the rate constant of water loss, is the dominating factor in the complexation processes.

Scheme 1 also shows that monoprotinated and deprotonated forms of the ligand react with $M(II)$ ions. Thus rate of the complexation reaction can be written as

$$\text{Rate} = k_{12}[\text{HN}^+-\text{O}^-][\text{M}(II)] + k_{43}[\text{N}-\text{O}^-][\text{M}(II)] \quad (16)$$

Since $k_{12} \ll k_{43}$ (Table 2),

$$\text{Rate} = k_{43}[\text{M}(II)][\text{L}] \quad (17)$$

From equations (15) and (17) and knowing the value of k_{os} from Fuoss equation⁷, the value

Fig. 1 Plots of $k_{obs} \{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1[\text{H}^+] + K_1K_2\}/K_1[\text{H}^+]$ vs $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ for Ni^{II} -L-2-aminobutanedioic acid-4-amide interaction at different temperatures.

of water exchange constant (k_o) can be calculated. These values are reported in Table 1.

Interaction of Cu^{II} with L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide : Kinetics of the complexation of Cu^{II} with L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide was studied in the pH range 2.01–3.02 to avoid hydrolysis. The pH was adjusted by dropwise addition of KOH/HNO_3 in conjunction with a pH meter (Radiometer pHM 26, Copenhagen). After the reaction, change in the pH (~ 0.1 unit) was observed and the values reported are those of the reaction mixtures. The temperatures were

maintained at 25–40° ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). In this case, the absorbance changes were large enough to be monitored directly without using any indicator and were traced out from the oscilloscope for each run. From the linear plot of $\log \Delta V$ vs time, pseudo-first order rate constant (k'_{obs}) values were calculated and second order rate constant (k_{obs}) values (Table 2) were calculated from the relation,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k'_{obs}}{[\text{M}(II)]}$$

In case of Cu^{II} -L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide interaction, equation (13) is valid as the plots of the left-hand-side values of equation (13) vs $[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$ at different temperatures were found to be linear (figure not shown). The values of k_{12} and k_{43} (Table 1) are obtained by the same way as in the previous case. Linear plots of $\log k$ and $\log k/T$ vs $1/T$ were used for evaluating activation parameter values. The values of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger corresponding to k_{12} and k_{43} steps for the reaction Cu -L-2-aminobutanedioic acid-4-amide were found to be 18.24, 8.99 kJ mol^{-1} and -130.92 , $-50.63 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. The values of k_o (Table 1) were obtained using equations (15) and (17).

Comparison of rate constants corresponding to the complexation of L-2-aminobutanedioic acid-4-amide with Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II} : Values of specific rate constants corresponding to protonated and deprotonated forms of the ligand are much larger in case of Cu^{II} as compared to Ni^{II} and Co^{II} . In every case, the values (Table 1) show that the deprotonated form of the ligand is more reactive than the protonated form. The large value of k_o in case of Cu^{II} as compared to Ni^{II} and Co^{II} (Table 1) can be explained on the basis of activation parameter values. In the case of Cu^{II} , activation energy is much less as compared to Ni^{II} and Co^{II} .

The fast complexation reaction in case of Cu^{II} can also be explained on the basis of crystal field stabilisation energy⁸. The loss of water molecule from the metal ion hydration sphere changes the geometry of the metal ion from

TABLE 1—VALUES OF k_{12} AND k_{43} FOR THE INTERACTION OF Ni^{II} , Co^{II} AND Cu^{II} WITH L-2-AMINO BUTANEDIOIC ACID 4-AMIDE

Temp.	Ni^{II} -L-Asparagine			Co^{II} -L-Asparagine			Cu^{II} -L-Asparagine		
	$k_{12} \times 10^{-2}$ $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	$k_{43} \times 10^{-4}$ $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	$k_0 \times 10^{-4}$ s^{-1}	$k_{12} \times 10^{-2}$ $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	$k_{43} \times 10^{-4}$ $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	$k_0 \times 10^{-4}$ s^{-1}	$k_{12} \times 10^{-2}$ $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	$k_{43} \times 10^{-4}$ $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	$k_0 \times 10^{-4}$ s^{-1}
25	0.95	2.29	1.15	8.10	6.73	3.39	5.8	3.8	1.92
30	1.40	2.60	1.31	9.40	7.31	3.69	6.6	4.17	2.11
35	2.20	2.93	1.48	11.10	8.15	4.12	7.4	4.41	2.20
40	3.05	3.23	1.63	13.10	8.79	4.42	8.6	4.78	2.40

TABLE 2—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE INTERACTION OF Ni^{II} , Co^{II} AND Cu^{II} WITH L-2-AMINO BUTANEDIOIC ACID 4-AMIDE AT DIFFERENT pH'S AND TEMPERATURES

$I = 0.1 M KNO_3$		$[L-Asparagine] = 3.33 \times 10^{-3} M$		$[L-Asparagine] = 4.61 \times 10^{-3} M$	
$[L-Asparagine] = 5.24 \times 10^{-3} M$		$[Co^{II}] = 2.66 \times 10^{-2} M$		$[Cu^{II}] = 4.78 \times 10^{-2} M$	
$[Ni^{II}] = 3.32 \times 10^{-2} M$		pH	$k_{obs} \times 10^{-2}$ $M^{-1}s^{-1}$	pH	$k_{obs} \times 10^{-2}$ $M^{-1}s^{-1}$
Temp. = 25°					
6.25	1.71	6.30	10.42	2.01	7.00
6.47	2.24	6.46	11.91	2.24	7.73
6.55	2.48	6.58	12.82	2.42	8.44
6.61	2.67	6.66	13.89	2.56	9.28
6.72	3.20	6.83	16.67	2.68	10.31
6.83	3.93	7.06	22.80	2.79	13.61
6.95	4.80	—	—	3.02	—
7.12	6.70	—	—	—	—
Temp. = 30°					
6.26	2.57	6.15	11.91	2.25	8.40
6.45	3.06	6.40	13.89	2.43	9.28
6.57	3.93	6.52	15.16	2.55	10.31
6.70	4.74	6.63	16.67	2.71	11.60
6.85	6.10	6.80	20.84	2.81	13.30
6.97	7.45	7.04	29.50	3.01	17.62
7.11	9.80	—	—	—	—
Temp. = 35°					
6.25	3.94	6.08	13.89	2.23	9.88
6.48	5.21	6.20	15.16	2.38	10.54
6.55	5.60	6.34	16.67	2.48	11.59
6.61	6.14	6.46	18.53	2.61	13.30
6.68	6.80	6.65	23.19	2.76	15.46
6.81	8.30	6.81	27.78	3.01	22.10
6.98	11.13	6.99	37.00	—	—
7.08	13.90	—	—	—	—
Temp. = 40°					
6.21	5.21	5.97	16.20	2.20	11.59
6.42	6.50	6.05	16.67	2.38	13.30
6.52	7.45	6.17	18.53	2.56	15.46
6.59	8.30	6.30	20.89	2.72	18.58
6.78	11.13	6.52	24.80	2.87	23.19
6.92	13.90	6.74	33.35	3.00	28.90
7.02	17.57	6.87	40.20	—	—

octahedral to trigonal bipyramidal. The difference in CFSE (Oh-TBP) in case of Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II} is 5.73, 2.55 and 1.09 Dq respectively. These values show that activation energy barrier is minimum in case of Cu^{II} which supports the highest value of k_{43} in case of Cu^{II} . The decreasing order of water exchange rate constant, $\text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$, found in the present work, is in agreement with the C.F.S.E. and also k_0 values are in agreement with the nmr data⁹.

Experimental

L-2-Aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide (Ubichem., A.R.), bromothymol blue (B.D.H.), 2,6-lutidine (Merck Schuscharadt), $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (all Merck) were used as such. Other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Freshly prepared solution of L-2-aminobutanedioic acid 4-amide was used for all complexation reactions and triple-distilled water was used in the preparation of all solutions.

Methods : Kinetic measurement were made on an Aminco-Morrow stopped-flow spectrophotometer under pseudo-first order conditions by taking the metal ion concentration in excess to the ligand concentration. The driving syringes and the reaction chamber were thermostated at $25\text{--}40^\circ$ ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) with an immersion type thermostat (German model NBE). In the reaction chamber, solutions of metal ions having ionic strength $I = 0.1 M$ and at desired pHs, buffered with 2,6-lutidine and HCl, were mixed with a solution

of L-2-aminobutanedioic acid-4-amide (containing bromothymol blue as an indicator) at the same pH and ionic strength as that of the metal ion. A slight change in the pH (~ 0.05 unit) was observed after mixing and the reported values are those of the reaction mixtures.

In case of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} the complex formation was monitored at 620 nm by pH indicator method¹ and in case of Cu^{II} at 600 nm without using any indicator as the absorbance changes were large enough to be monitored directly. Blank experiments in which (i) indicator and metal ion solution and (ii) indicator and ligand solution were mixed showed no absorbance change to interfere with the results of complexation reactions.

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